

Beyond Association: Evaluating the Predictive Utility of Anemia in Heart Failure Using Survival Models and Multivariable Risk Adjustment

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Abstract

Background: Anemia is a common comorbidity in heart failure (HF) and is associated with adverse clinical outcomes. This study assessed the prevalence of anemia in HF patients and its prognostic significance on mortality and recurrence.

Methods: This retrospective cross-sectional observational study was conducted at Amrita Institute of Medical Sciences using electronic medical records from January 2017 to January 2020. A total of 150 patients diagnosed with HF with complete laboratory and echocardiographic data were included. Demographic, clinical, laboratory, echocardiographic, and medication-related variables were analyzed. Statistical analysis included Chi-square test, Mann–Whitney U test, binary logistic regression, Kaplan–Meier survival analysis, log-rank test, and Cox regression.

Results: Among 150 HF patients, 43 (28.7%) were anemic. Anemia was significantly associated with older age ($p=0.046$), diabetes mellitus ($p=0.032$), normal heart rate ($p=0.032$), abnormal packed cell volume ($p<0.001$), elevated serum creatinine ($p=0.017$), and normal LVEDD ($p=0.020$). Overall survival did not differ significantly between anemic and non-anemic patients. Abnormal serum creatinine ($p=0.040$) and advanced NYHA class ($p=0.050$) independently predicted mortality, while abnormal creatinine and valvular heart disease predicted recurrence.

Conclusion: Anemia is prevalent in HF patients but does not independently predict mortality or recurrence. Renal dysfunction and HF severity remain the strongest prognostic indicators.

Keywords: Heart Failure, Haemoglobin, Medical records, Survival, Recurrence, Mortality, Prognosis.

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Introduction

Heart failure (HF) is a major global health challenge characterized by the heart's inability to pump sufficient blood to meet metabolic demands, leading to significant morbidity and mortality worldwide.^{[1],[2]} Anemia, a frequent comorbidity affecting nearly one-third of HF patients, has been associated with increased symptoms, reduced exercise tolerance, and higher hospitalization and mortality rates.^{[3],[4],[5]} The interplay between anemia and HF is multifactorial, involving renal dysfunction, inflammation, and iron deficiency.^{[6],[7]} This study aims to determine the prevalence of anemia in HF and evaluate its prognostic significance on clinical outcomes.^{[8],[9]}

Materials and methods

Study setting

The study was conducted in the department of Biostatistics with the help of department of cardiology at Amrita Institute of Medical Sciences, Kochi during January 2020. Cross-sectional design was used for the study. The data was collected from the Electronic medical record data of cardiology department were used for the study. Participants visiting cardiology department with heart failure with full laboratory and echocardiography data in their medical record were selected for the study. Those who did not have full laboratory and echocardiography data in their medical records were excluded from the study.

Sample Size

Based on the prevalence of anemia (41.9%) in heart failure patients observed in an earlier publication, (Anemia in severe heart failure patients: does it predict prognosis? Tamrat Befekadu Abebe, Eyob Alemayehu Gebreyohannes, Akshaya Srikanth Bhagavathula, Yonas Getaye Tefera and Tadesse Melaku Abegaz, Abebe et al. BMC Cardiovascular Disorders (2017) 17:248 DOI 10.1186/s12872-017-0680-5) based on the formula given below and with 20% allowable error and 95% confidence, the minimum sample size comes to 135,

$$n = \frac{z_{(1-\frac{\alpha}{2})}^2 p(1-p)}{d^2}$$

p - Expected prevalence of the event in the study group

d - Expected absolute allowable error in the p

$z_{(1-\frac{\alpha}{2})}$ - Value of the normal deviate at considered level of confidence

Data Collection

A total of 150 cardiac patients who were having heart failure were included in my present study. Details about the patients were collected using electronic medical data with prior permission from the medical director, principal and cardiology in-charge. It was a cross-sectional, single-centered observational study. Since it was a retrospective study, to obtain the required sample size the data was collected from January 2017 to January 2020 and The ethical approval of the study (Ref. N: IRB-AIMS-2020-204). The study population comprised of all the patients having heart failure with and without anemia and those who had registered in the adult cardiology within 3 years. Patients only with diagnosed heart failure and those who have only full laboratory and echocardiography results were included where as those with incomplete data are excluded from the study.

As part of evaluation, the following parameters were analysed such as Age, Date of treatment, Status, Recurrence, Date of Recurrence, Date of death, Gender, Weight, NYHA class, Hypertension, Diabetics, AF, Heart Rate, Systolic BP, Diastolic BP, Etiology, Lab parameters like (Hb, Creatinine). Echocardiography details and Medication profile were noted. These corresponding variables of patients diagnosed with heart failure were collected from the adult cardiology based on the required sample size.

Statistical analysis

Statistical analysis was performed using IBM SPSS 20.0 software. Categorical variables are expressed using frequency and percentage. Continuous variables are presented by mean, standard deviation and standard error. To test the statistical significance of the difference in the mean and median weight between two groups, Mann - Whitney U test was used.^[10]

To find the predictors of Anemia first we test the statistical significance of the difference in the proportion of categorical factors between two groups (Anemic and Non-Anemic), for that Chi Square (χ^2) test with Fisher's exact test and Pearson's χ^2 test was used.^[11] Variables which had p-value less than 0.05 i.e., which are statistically significant were considered and to find the most significant predictor of Anemia binary logistic regression analysis was used.

To find the overall and recurrence free survival of various factors, Kaplan -Meier (KM) analysis was used and comparison was done by log rank test.^{[12],[13]} To find the most significant predictor of mortality and recurrence Cox Regression analysis was used.

Ethical Considerations

Ethical approval for this study was obtained from the Institutional Review Board of Amrita Institute of Medical Sciences (Ref. No: IRB-AIMS-2020-204). As this was a retrospective study based on anonymized patient records, informed consent was waived. All patient data were

handled with strict confidentiality in accordance with the Declaration of Helsinki and institutional ethical standards.

Results

Patient Demographics and Clinical Characteristics

A total of 150 patients diagnosed with heart failure were enrolled in this study. The mean age of participants was 68.4 ± 11.8 years. Of these, 43 patients (28.7%) were anemic, and 107 (71.3%) were non-anemic. Age distribution analysis showed that 15 patients (10.0%) were ≤ 50 years old, 64 (42.7%) were between 51 and 70 years, and 71 (47.3%) were above 70 years. There were 55 females (36.7%) and 95 males (63.3%) in the cohort.

Regarding etiology, 71 patients (47.3%) had ischemic heart disease (IHD), 27 (18.0%) had valvular heart disease (VHD), 8 (5.3%) had hypertensive heart disease (HHD), 5 (3.3%) had dilated cardiomyopathy (DCMP), and 39 (26.0%) fell into other etiological categories. Based on the New York Heart Association (NYHA) classification, 14 patients (9.3%) were class I, 46 (30.7%) were class II, and 90 (60.0%) were class III/IV. (Table 1)

Recurrence and Mortality

During the follow-up period, 42 patients (28.0%) experienced recurrence of heart failure, while 108 (72.0%) did not. A total of 133 patients (88.7%) survived and 17 (11.3%) died during the observation period.

Distribution Of Patients According To Medication Results

Out of 150 cardiac patients, 134(89.3%) are using Diuretics, 16(10.7%) are not using Diuretics, 81(54%) are using Spironolactone,69(46%) are not using Spironolactone, 42(28%) are using Beta blocker,108(72%) are not using Beta blocker, 31(20.7%) are using Digoxin, 119(79.3%)

are not using Digoxin, 81(54%) are using Antiplatelet, 69(46%) are not using Antiplatelet, 34(22.7%) are using Anticoagulant, 116(77.3%) are not using Anticoagulant, 58(38.7%) are using Statin, 92(61.3%) are not using Statin, 24(16%) are using Sacubitril, 126(84%) are not using Sacubitril, 16(10.7%) are using Oral iron, 134(89.3%) are not using Oral iron. Out of 43 cardiac patients who have anemia, 16(37.2%) patients are using Spironolactone compared to those who are nonanemic, 65(60.7%). The result shows statistically significant (p value =0.015).

Out of 43 cardiac patients who have anemia, 4(9.3%) patients are using Digoxin compared to those who are nonanemic, 27(25.2%). The result shows statistically significant (p value =0.050).

Out of 43 cardiac patients who have anemia, 4(9.3%) patients are using Anticoagulant compared to those who are non anemic, 30(28.0%). The result shows statistically significant (p value =0.024).

Out of 43 cardiac patients who have anemia, 10(23.3%) patients are using Oral Iron compared to those who are nonanemic, 6(5.6%) The result shows statistically significant (p value =0.004).

Other factors are not statistically significant. (Table 2)

Association of Age with Anemia

Among the 43 anemic patients, 1 (2.3%) was aged 31–50 years, 16 (37.2%) were aged 51–70 years, and 26 (60.5%) were over 70 years. There was a statistically significant association between age group and anemia status ($p = 0.046$). (Table 3)

Comparison of Clinical, Laboratory, and Echocardiographic Parameters

Of the total cohort, 92 patients (61.3%) had hypertension, 97 (64.7%) had diabetes mellitus, 60 (40%) had atrial fibrillation, 113 (75.3%) had a normal heart rate, 87 (58.0%) had a normal systolic blood pressure, and 114 (76.0%) had a normal diastolic blood pressure.

Compared to non-anemic patients, those with anemia were more likely to be diabetic (79.1% vs. 58.9%; $p = 0.032$), less likely to have atrial fibrillation (18.6% vs. 48.6%; $p = 0.032$), and more likely to present with a normal heart rate (88.4% vs. 70.1%; $p = 0.032$). Other clinical parameters like hypertension did not show statistically significant differences between groups.

In laboratory and echocardiographic measures, none of the anemic patients had a normal packed cell volume (PCV), whereas 39 (36.4%) non-anemic patients did ($p < 0.001$). Normal serum creatinine was observed in 13 (30.2%) anemic patients versus 57 (53.3%) non-anemic patients ($p = 0.017$). Normal left ventricular end-diastolic dimension (LVEDD) was seen in 17 (39.5%) anemic patients and 21 (19.6%) non-anemic individuals ($p = 0.020$).showed statistical significance.

Other factors like LVEF, creatinine clearance and sodium did not show statistical significance

Survival and Recurrence Analysis

The mean overall survival time was significantly greater for patients with normal creatinine (28.7 ± 1.9 months) compared to those with abnormal creatinine levels (20.7 ± 1.8 months; $p < 0.05$; (Fig 1).

Recurrence-free survival was significantly higher in females (28.4 ± 2.0 months) than in males (21.4 ± 1.7 months; $p < 0.05$), and in those with normal creatinine (33.7 ± 1.1 months) compared to those with abnormal creatinine (29.6 ± 1.6 months; $p < 0.05$) (Fig 2)

The results show patient with anemia and non anemic have no statistically significant difference in the overall survival (Table 4)

None of the other parameters like demographics, etiology, NYHA class factors, laboratory parameters (except cr levels), clinical parameters show statistical significance on the overall survival.

Predictors of Mortality and Recurrences

On Cox regression analysis for overall survival, abnormal creatinine emerged as the most significant independent predictor of mortality ($p = 0.040$, 95% CI: 1.06–10.73), followed by NYHA class ($p = 0.05$, 95% CI: 1.01–7.51). The use of diuretics was not a significant predictor.(Table 5)

For recurrence-free survival, significant predictors included abnormal creatinine ($p = 0.026$, 95% CI: 1.10–4.39) and the presence of valvular heart disease ($p = 0.033$, 95% CI: 1.06–4.44). Gender was not a statistically significant predictor of recurrence.(Table 6)

Discussion and Conclusion

This study investigated the prevalence and prognostic implications of anemia among patients with heart failure (HF) admitted to Amrita Institute of Medical Sciences, Kochi. The prevalence of anemia was 28.7%, which aligns with several previous studies but is lower than those conducted in low-income countries such as Cameroon, Ethiopia, and Uganda, where prevalence rates were reported as 49.5%, 49.8%, and 64%, respectively.^{[14],[15],[16]} This variation may be attributed to differences in population characteristics, socioeconomic conditions, and criteria used to define anemia.^{[17],[18]} The prevalence increased significantly with age, as 60.5% of anemic patients were older than 70 years, consistent with prior studies showing that anemia is more common in elderly HF patients with multiple comorbidities.^[19]

The primary finding of this study was that anemia, though common, did not independently predict mortality or recurrence in HF patients. Elevated serum creatinine and advanced NYHA class were the most significant predictors of mortality ($p = 0.040$ and $p = 0.05$, respectively). Diabetes mellitus, normal heart rate, and reduced renal function were associated with anemia, and anemic patients were less likely to be prescribed ACE inhibitors and spironolactone. These results are consistent with previous reports by Abebe et al. and Owan et al., which identified

renal dysfunction and disease severity as stronger determinants of prognosis than anemia itself [20],[8]

The study's strengths include the use of real-world hospital data and detailed evaluation of clinical, laboratory, and echocardiographic factors. The design allowed meaningful assessment of HF outcomes within a defined population. Nevertheless, as a retrospective single-center study, it carries inherent limitations such as selection bias, incomplete documentation, and lack of causal inference. The absence of longitudinal hemoglobin monitoring and anemia management data limits evaluation of treatment effects, and the relatively small sample size may affect generalizability.

The findings support the concept that anemia in HF primarily reflects underlying pathophysiological burden rather than acting as an independent cause of adverse outcomes. Chronic kidney disease, inflammation, and neurohormonal activation play a central role in the pathogenesis of anemia, making renal dysfunction a key confounding factor.^{[21],[22]} Previous studies such as EVEREST, IN-CHF, and ANCHOR have shown that anemic HF patients often receive suboptimal doses of evidence-based therapies like ACE inhibitors and beta-blockers due to renal impairment.^{[23],[24],[25]} Our results corroborate these observations, emphasizing the need for careful renal function monitoring and personalized therapy in HF management.

The prognostic role of anemia in HF remains controversial. Although correction of anemia can improve exercise tolerance and quality of life, survival benefit has not been consistently demonstrated. This study supports the growing evidence that anemia acts more as a marker of disease severity than a direct mediator of poor outcomes. Mechanisms include impaired erythropoietin production, iron deficiency, chronic inflammation, and hemo-dilution, along with renin–angiotensin–aldosterone system activation.^[14] Hence, therapeutic focus should

remain on managing renal dysfunction and optimizing HF therapy rather than targeting anemia alone.

Future multicentric, prospective studies with larger cohorts are needed to validate these findings across populations. Longitudinal assessment of hemoglobin, iron status, and renal biomarkers may elucidate causal pathways linking anemia correction and HF prognosis. Interventional studies on iron therapy, erythropoiesis-stimulating agents, and reno protective treatments could clarify therapeutic value. Systematic reviews and meta-analyses integrating global evidence would further guide patient management and policy recommendations.

In conclusion, anemia is prevalent among HF patients but does not independently predict mortality or recurrence. Renal dysfunction and NYHA class are the dominant predictors of poor outcomes, highlighting the importance of integrated management strategies that address both cardiac and renal health.

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Conflict of Interest

The authors declare that there are no conflicts of interest related to this study. No financial or personal relationships have influenced the research or preparation of this manuscript.

Authorship Confirmation

All authors meet the criteria for authorship as outlined by the International Committee of Medical Journal Editors (ICMJE).

All authors have read and approved the final version of the manuscript. Each author confirms that the manuscript represents honest, original work and that all data have been accurately presented.

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Tables and figures

Table 1. Demographic Variables

Parameter	Number of Patients (n)	Percentage (%)
Age (mean \pm SD)	68.4 \pm 11.8 years	
Anemia Status		
– Anemic	43	28.7%
– Non-anemic	107	71.3%
Age Distribution		
– \leq 50 years	15	10.0%
– 51–70 years	64	42.7%
– $>$ 70 years	71	47.3%
Gender		
– Male	95	63.3%
– Female	55	36.7%
Etiology of Heart Failure		
– Ischemic Heart Disease (IHD)	71	47.3%
– Valvular Heart Disease (VHD)	27	18.0%
– Hypertensive Heart Disease (HHD)	8	5.3%
– Dilated Cardiomyopathy (DCMP)	5	3.3%
– Others	39	26.0%
NYHA Functional Classification		
– Class I	14	9.3%
– Class II	46	30.7%

Parameter	Number of Patients (n)	Percentage (%)
– Class III/IV	90	60.0%
Follow up outcomes		
Recurrence of Heart Failure	42	28%
No Recurrence	108	72%
Survived	133	88.7%
Died	17	11.3%

Table 2. Comparison Of Medications Between Anemic And Nonanemic

Variable	Category	Anemia		p-value
		Yes n=43(%)	No n=107(%)	
Diuretics	Yes	38(88.4)	96(89.7)	1.000
	No	5(11.6)	11(10.3)	
Spironolactone	Yes	16(37.2)	65(60.7)	0.015
	No	27(62.8)	42(39.3)	
Beta Blocker	Yes	11(25.6)	31(29.0)	0.828
	No	32(74.4)	76(71.0)	
Digoxin	Yes	4(9.3)	27(25.2)	0.050
	No	39(90.7)	80(74.8)	
Antiplatelet	Yes	24(55.8)	57(53.3)	0.919
	No	19(44.2)	50(46.7)	
Anticoagulant	Yes	4(9.3)	30(28.0)	0.024
	No	39(90.7)	77(72.0)	
Statin	Yes	20(46.5)	38(35.5)	0.287

	No	23(53.5)	69(64.5)	
Sacubitril	Yes	4(9.3)	20(18.7)	0.241
	No	39(90.7)	87(81.3)	
Oral Iron	Yes	10(23.3)	6(5.6)	0.004
	No	33(76.7)	101(94.4)	

Table 3. Association Age Between Anemic And Nonanemic

Age	Anemia		p-value
	Yes n(%)	No n(%)	
31-50(15)	1(6.7)	14(93.3)	0.046
51-70(64)	16(25.0)	48(75.0)	
71-90(71)	26(36.6)	45(63.4)	

Table 4. Impact of Anemia on Overall Survival

Anemia	N	Mean Survival Time	S. E	p-value
Yes	43	25.27	1.59	0.147
No	107	32.46	1.06	

Table 5. Cox Regression Analysis For Overall Survival

Variables	B	S.E.	Wald	p-value	Hazard Ratio	95% C.I for Hazard Ratio	
						Lower	Upper
Abnormal Creatinine level	1.21	0.59	4.20	0.047	3.36	1.06	10.73
NYHA Class (1)	-0.52	1.08	0.24	0.628	0.59	0.07	4.88
NYHA Class (2)	1.01	0.51	3.94	0.047	2.76	1.01	7.51
NYHA Class (3&4)			4.85	0.09	1.00	-	-
Absence of Diuretics	-13.14	535.80	0.00	0.980	0.00	0.00	

Table 6. Cox Regression Analysis For Recurrence Free Survival

Variables	B	S.E.	Wald	p-value	Odds Ratio	95% C.I for Odds Ratio	
						Lower	Upper
Abnormal Creatinine level	0.787	0.353	4.968	0.026	2.196	1.100	4.386
VHD (VHD)	0.776	0.364	4.543	0.033	2.173	1.064	4.435
Gender (Female)	-0.646	0.368	3.077	0.079	0.524	0.255	1.079

Figure 1 Comparison of Creatinine Level With Overall Survival

Figure 2 Comparison of Creatinine With Recurrence Free Survival